

“RESEARCH-BASED TRANSFORMATION OF TEACHER EDUCATION: TRADITION AS A BASIS FOR INNOVATION”

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REFLECTIVE TECHNOLOGY FOR TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The purpose of this article is to describe reflective technology for teaching foreign languages. The article analyzes various points of view on the definition of the concept of “reflection”, considered by scientists of philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy, and proposes the author’s definition of reflection from the point of view of methods of teaching foreign languages. Reflection on the purpose of implementation is described: reflection on the mood and emotional state of students, reflection on the assimilation of the content of educational material by students, reflection on the form of student activity.*

Key words: *technology, reflection, education, activity, foreign language, analysis, self-education.*

Reflexive technology is a technology that promotes the formation, development, improvement and consolidation of students’ knowledge, skills, abilities and relevant competencies in acquisition of foreign languages.

“Reflection” translated from Latin (*reflexio*) according to reference literature, means, the ability of the mental organ to reflect the surrounding reality and itself.... it is a source of internal experience, a means of self-knowledge and a necessary tool for thinking; this is a person’s readiness and ability for self-esteem, self-knowledge, analysis of one’s actions, motives, actions, mood, and comparison of them with the actions and actions of other people [5].

It should be noted that in scientific use the term “reflection” was first used by the English educator and philosopher John Locke in the 17 th century in the book “An essay concerning Human Understanding”, which he wrote over 20 years [10].

John Locke defines reflection as “...the observation to which the mind subjects its activities and the manner in which they are manifested, whereby ideas of those activities arise in the mind...a person is a rational thinking being who has a mind, and reflection can regard itself as itself...”. He further notes, “...follow a child from his birth and observe the changes produced by time, and you will see how, thanks to the

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feelings, the soul is more and more enriched with ideas, more and more awakened, thinks the more intensely, the more it has material for thinking” [4].

The American scientist Pierre Teilhard de Chardin defines reflection as the ability acquired by consciousness to focus on oneself and master oneself as an object that has its own specific stability and its own specific meaning - the ability not just to know, but to know oneself; not just know, but know that you know [8].

In the book “Psychology of Human Development” we find the following definition of reflection: “Reflection is such a specifically human ability that allows a person to make his thoughts, emotional states, his actions and relationships, in general his whole self, the subject of special consideration (analysis and evaluation) and practical transformation (change and development)” [7].

Thus, from a psychological point of view, reflection is a process of self-analysis of one’s own mental states, helping students formulate the results obtained, determine goals for further development, and adjust the directions of self-education and self-development.

From a philosophical point of view, the essence of the concept of “reflection” comes down to three main processes: as a process of turning back; as a process of self-knowledge by a person of his own mental qualities and state; as a process of understanding social reality in the process of socialization [1].

So, for example, according to the Russian philosopher G.P. Shchedrovitsky, reflection is a process and mechanism for the reproduction of activity [6].

In pedagogy V.V. Davydov, V.A. Slavenin, T.I. Shamova consider reflection as a pedagogical definition. They describe it as a professional ability, associate it with professional competence, and explore the role of reflection in the successful activities of teachers in a multidimensional way. L. Zankov, I. Yakimanskaya consider reflection as an element of developmental teaching technology, which is successfully used in school practice [9].

According to A.V. Khutorskoy, reflection is the process and result of awareness of the totality of activities occurring during a lesson. The subject of reflection can be both the subject’s own activity and any other activity in the lesson, including their interrelations. One of the tasks of reflection is to find out what actually happened in the lesson? Is this really what was intended, or what this or that lesson participant thinks. Reflection is quite subjective, i.e. for different subjects of the lesson, different meanings of the same action or activity may be visible. It is the finding of differences in this understanding that is one of the driving forces of reflection - its instrument of

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influence on the educational process, on the harmonization of the understandings of its different subjects [2].

Thus, in pedagogy, reflection is considered as a process of thinking and activity. Pedagogical reflection is the integration of processes of research into one's activities, which enriches professional and pedagogical experience.

A study of the literature on reflection allows us to conclude that reflection is studied as a philosophical category and is also studied by such disciplines as pedagogy and psychology. We adhere to the definition of reflection given by A.V. Khutorskiy, since the important thing in education is the process and result of awareness of the totality of students' activities occurring during a lesson. Based on scientists' definitions of reflection, we have developed our own definition. In our opinion, reflection is one of the main stages of the lesson, which involves a process of interrelated activities between the teacher and students to acquire knowledge, skills and abilities, during which students independently assess their state, emotions, knowledge, analyze the information received, the results of their activities on the subject being studied. Thus, from a methodological point of view, reflection is the process of organizing a lesson, where schoolteachers need to develop the reflective competence of students, increase the need for discussions on the topics being studied, and solving analytical, logical and creative problems.

The reflection stage is equally important for both the teacher and the student, since it helps the teacher determine the effectiveness and fruitfulness of his work, and the students - the degree of assimilation of the program material, contributes to the formation of critical, creative, analytical, logical thinking, the development of self-education and self-control.

As practice shows, if a student understands why he is studying a given topic, how it will be useful to him in the future; what goals should be achieved in this lesson; what contribution he can make to the common cause; if students can adequately evaluate his work and the work of his classmates, then the learning process becomes much more interesting and easier for both the student and the teacher.

When conducting the reflection stage, the teacher must take into account the age and individual characteristics of students, remember that reflection is always creativity, therefore it is necessary to use different techniques and methods in the lesson. It is wrong to think that reflection should be carried out only at the end of the lesson. You can organize reflective activity of students at any stage of the lesson,

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when asking about homework, studying a new topic, consolidating, summing up the lesson.

According to the purpose of the conducting, there are three types of reflection: reflection of the mood and emotional state of students, reflection on the assimilation of the content of educational material by students, reflection on the form of student activity [3].

Reflection of the mood and emotional state of students - it is a type of reflection that contributes to the formation of a favorable microclimate in the classroom. It is advisable to conduct such reflection at the beginning of the lesson in order to establish emotional contact or at the end as a stage of summing up the lesson.

Reflection on the mood and emotional state of students is multivariate and is not difficult to carry out. It assesses the emotional mood of students and their perception of educational material. This is a reflection from the categories “liked/disliked”, “interesting/boring”, and “it was fun/sad”.

Reflection on the assimilation of the content of educational material by students - it is a type of reflection at the end of a lesson, where it is important for the teacher not only to find out and understand the emotional state of students at the end of the lesson, but also how productive the lesson has become for them, how firmly the students have mastered the content of the educational material. Students need to evaluate their activity in the lesson, the usefulness and interestingness of the forms of presenting knowledge, the fascination of the lesson, and teamwork.

Reflection on the form of student activity – it is a reflection, which contributes to the analysis of students’ activities in the lesson, identifying existing problems on the topic being studied, used at the stage of checking homework, defending project, research and independent work, at the stage of consolidating the material. This reflection can be collective, group, frontal, or individual.

At this stage of reflection, the student must not only understand the content of the material, but also comprehend his activities in the lesson, the methods and techniques of his work. What I did? For what purpose? Why am I doing it this way? What result did I get? Which option is better? These are the questions that students who master reflection ask themselves, i.e. able to understand their activities.

All of the above allows us to conclude that reflection is a process of constant analysis of one’s own activities and its results. The use of reflection techniques in a foreign language lesson makes the process of teaching languages more effective and interesting, allowing you to analyze the successes of students, determine their

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weaknesses and strengths, promoting awareness of the learning goal, which is a motivational factor for learning a foreign language.

List of used literature:

1. Averina L.V., Borovkova T.I. and others, Pedagogy. Nizhny Novgorod: NOO "Professional Science", 2018.
2. Khutorskoy A.V. Analysis, introspection and reflection of the lesson <http://khutorskoy.ru/be/2008/0312/index.htm>.
3. Kurbatova O.V., Krasnoperova L.B., Soldatenko S.A. Reflection on a training session: methodological aspect. – Kemerovo, 2017.
4. Locke J. Works: in 3 volumes. T. 1 / ed. I.S. Narsky. M.: Mysl, 1985.
5. Romas L. Research activities in primary classes / L. Romas // Primary education. –2013. – No. 15 (April). – P. 2-11.
6. Shchedrovitsky G.P. Selected works. - M., 1995.
7. Slobodchikov V.I., Isaev E.I. Psychology of human development. - M., 2000.
8. Teilhard de Chardin P. The Phenomenon of Man. - M., 1987.
9. Yakimanskaya I. S. Development of technology for personality-oriented learning / I. S. Yakimanskaya // Questions of psychology. - 1995. - No. 2.
10. <https://ru.m.wikipedia.org>.